

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS IN TEACHER TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the relevance of socio-emotional competencies in teacher training, taking into account the contemporary challenges permeating the educational landscape and the increasing demands of teaching work. It is based on the premise that educators, in addition to mastering scientific and pedagogical content, must develop socio-emotional skills that promote conflict mediation, the creation of healthy learning environments, and the holistic development of students. The research is supported by a comprehensive literature review, including classic and contemporary authors, addressing socio-emotional competencies, teacher training, and the role of the school in the 21st century. Through direct and indirect citations, the theoretical analysis is enriched, offering a critical view of the importance of these competencies. The article concludes that the effective incorporation of socio-emotional competencies in initial and continuing teacher training is fundamental to promoting a more humane, critical, and effective pedagogical practice. This approach not only contributes to the professional development of educators, but also to the training of students better prepared to face the challenges of today's world, cultivating essential skills for coexistence and collaborative learning.

Keywords: Socio-emotional skills. Teacher training. Education. Teaching practice.

1. Introduction

Contemporary education faces complex challenges that go beyond the mere transmission of curricular content. Teachers are constantly required to deal with emotional, social, and behavioral issues that emerge in the daily school routine. In this context, socio-emotional skills become fundamental to teaching practice, as they contribute to building healthy interpersonal relationships, managing the classroom, and fostering the holistic development of students.

According to Delors (1996), education should be based on four pillars: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, and learning to be. These pillars highlight that the educational process involves cognitive, social, and emotional dimensions, reinforcing the importance of socio-emotional skills for both students and teachers. Thus, teacher training needs to consider these dimensions in an integrated way.

This article aims to analyze the importance of socio-emotional skills in teacher training, based on a theoretical framework that discusses the concepts, foundations, and implications of these skills for pedagogical practice. The relevance of the topic is justified by the need to rethink teacher training curricula in order to meet the demands of 21st-century education.

2 Methodology

The methodology adopted in this study is qualitative in nature, based on bibliographic research. Works, scientific articles, official documents, and academic productions addressing socio-emotional competencies, teacher training, and contemporary education were analyzed. The selection of authors prioritized classic and current references recognized in the fields of education and educational psychology.

The material was analyzed in a critical and interpretive manner, seeking to establish relationships between the concepts presented by the different authors. Direct and indirect quotations were used to provide a theoretical foundation for the discussions proposed throughout the article.

3. Socio-emotional skills: concepts and fundamentals

The concept of socio-emotional skills has been widely discussed in recent decades, especially in the field of education. According to Goleman (1995), socio-emotional skills are related to emotional intelligence, which involves the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. For the author, skills such as empathy, self-control, motivation, and social skills are crucial for personal and professional success.

Similarly, Mayer and Salovey (1997) define emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive, evaluate, and express emotions appropriately, as well as to use these emotions to facilitate thinking and problem-solving. This perspective reinforces the idea that emotions play a central role in learning processes and social interactions.

In the educational context, socio-emotional skills are understood as a set of abilities that allow individuals to effectively deal with the emotional and social demands of the school environment. According to the Brazilian National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC), these skills involve aspects such as self-awareness, empathy, responsibility, cooperation, and resilience (BRASIL, 2018).

4 Teacher training and contemporary challenges

Teacher training has been the subject of intense debate, especially in light of the social, cultural, and technological transformations that impact education. According to Nóvoa (1995), teacher training should be understood as a continuous process that articulates theoretical, practical, and experiential knowledge. In this sense, the socio-emotional dimension of the teacher cannot be neglected.

Tardif (2002) highlights that teachers' knowledge is constructed throughout their professional trajectory and is deeply related to experiences lived in the daily life of the school. The author states that "the teacher's work is human work about the human," which requires skills that go beyond mastery of disciplinary content (TARDIF, 2002, p. 35).

Given this scenario, initial and ongoing teacher training needs to include the development of socio-emotional skills that enable teachers to face stressful situations, interpersonal conflicts, and pedagogical challenges in a balanced and reflective way.

5. The importance of socio-emotional skills in teaching practice.

Socio-emotional skills play a central role in teaching practice, directly influencing the quality of interactions between teacher and students. According to Freire (1996), the act of teaching requires respect for the students' knowledge, dialogue, empathy, and ethical commitment. For the author, "teaching requires understanding that education is a form of intervention in the world" (FREIRE, 1996, p. 98).

In this sense, teachers who develop socio-emotional skills are better prepared to create a welcoming learning environment, fostering student engagement and knowledge construction. Furthermore, these skills contribute to conflict management and the promotion of relationships based on respect and cooperation.

Studies indicate that emotionally competent teachers have greater job satisfaction and lower burnout rates. According to Maslach and Leiter (1999), the ability to manage emotions

and interpersonal relationships is a protective factor against burnout, which is common in the teaching profession.

6 Socio-emotional skills in initial teacher training

Initial teacher training is a strategic moment for the development of socio-emotional skills. However, many undergraduate courses still prioritize theoretical and methodological content, to the detriment of the emotional and social dimensions of teaching.

According to Perrenoud (2000), training teachers involves developing professional skills that allow them to face complex and unpredictable situations. Among these skills, the ability to work in teams, to communicate effectively, and to reflect on one's own practice stand out, all of which are related to socio-emotional skills.

The inclusion of subjects, projects, and formative practices that explicitly address socio-emotional skills can contribute to a more comprehensive teacher training that is more consistent with the demands of contemporary education.

7. Ongoing training and socio-emotional development of teachers.

Continuing education is essential for improving socio-emotional skills throughout a teaching career. According to Imbernón (2011), ongoing training should promote spaces for collective reflection, exchange of experiences, and collaborative construction of knowledge.

These spaces allow teachers to share challenges, emotions, and coping strategies, strengthening personal and professional development. Furthermore, continuing education programs focused on socio-emotional development can contribute to improving the school climate and the quality of teaching.

8 Implications of socio-emotional skills for education

The emphasis on socio-emotional skills in teacher training has significant implications for education as a whole. Emotionally competent teachers tend to develop more inclusive, democratic, and sensitive teaching practices that meet students' needs.

Furthermore, these skills foster the development of a school culture based on dialogue, empathy, and respect for differences. As Delors (1996) points out, education should contribute

to the formation of individuals capable of living together in society in an ethical and supportive manner.

9. Final Considerations

The analysis presented in this article highlights that socio-emotional skills are fundamental to teacher training and the quality of education. Given contemporary challenges, it is essential to rethink training processes, systematically incorporating the development of these skills.

It is concluded that initial and ongoing teacher training should articulate cognitive, pedagogical, and socio-emotional knowledge, aiming at building a more humane, reflective, and transformative teaching practice. Investing in the socio-emotional development of teachers is, therefore, investing in the improvement of education and the holistic development of students.

References

BRAZIL. **National Common Curricular Base** . Brasília: MEC, 2018.

DELORS, J. **Education: a treasure to discover** . São Paulo: Cortez, 1996.

FREIRE, P. **Pedagogy of Autonomy: Necessary Knowledge for Educational Practice** . São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 1996.

GOLEMAN, D. **Emotional Intelligence** . Rio de Janeiro: Objetiva, 1995.

IMBERNÓN, F. **Teacher and professional training: training for change and uncertainty** . São Paulo: Cortez, 2011.

MASLACH, C.; LEITER, MP. **Work and wear and tear: the challenge of burnout** . Porto Alegre: Artmed, 1999.

MAYER, J.D.; SALOVEY, P. What is emotional intelligence? In: SALOVEY, P.; SLUYTER, D. (org.). **Emotional development and emotional intelligence** . New York: Basic Books, 1997.

NÓVOA, A. **Teachers and their training** . Lisbon: Dom Quixote, 1995.

PERRENOUD, P. **Ten new competencies for teaching** . Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2000.

TARDIF, M. **Teacher knowledge and professional training** . Petrópolis: Vozes, 2002.